

Uzbekistan as a tourist destination for creating new projects

Usmanova Dildora Rustamovna

the master of the Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship of the
Department of “BUSINESS MANAGEMENT (MBA)”

Abstract:

Uzbekistan is a country of the greatest cities with hundreds of architectural monuments of different eras. Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shakhrisabz, Termez and Kokand are known throughout the world. These cities, the same age as Rome and Babylon, were once the largest centers of science and culture. The best minds and hands of that time flocked to them. The world was amazed by the luxury and splendor of palaces, minarets, mosques, and mausoleums created by famous architects of the past. World-famous monuments of ancient architecture still remember the times of the conquests of Alexander the Great and Genghis Khan where anyone can create new project based on tourism.

Key words: Great Silk Road, world-famous monuments, comfortable and safe stay for tourists in these historical cities, cultural heritage, various types of art.

Uzbekistan is a country located in the center of the Great Silk Road, on the territory of the vast Central Asian region with a history dating back almost a million years. Uzbekistan is a state with a unique cultural heritage, various types of art and traditional crafts, the mentality of the population, its folklore, and cuisine. All this distinguishes it favorably from neighboring countries and regions.

Recently, interest in Uzbekistan as a tourist destination has increased significantly, and accordingly, the range of tourism services provided by local tour operators is increasing from year to year to attract more travelers. The bulk of travelers in Uzbekistan are residents of the countries of the European Commonwealth, as well as some countries of the Asia-Pacific region.

Uzbekistan is a country of the greatest cities with hundreds of architectural monuments of different eras. Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shakhrisabz, Termez and Kokand are known throughout the world. These cities, the same age as Rome and Babylon, were once the largest centers of science and culture. The best minds and hands of that time flocked to them. The world was amazed by the luxury and splendor of palaces, minarets, mosques, and mausoleums created by famous

architects of the past. World-famous monuments of ancient architecture still remember the times of the conquests of Alexander the Great and Genghis Khan. Alas, we have to admit that many of these masterpieces simply have not survived to the present day, or only show their majestic ruins to the eyes of others. But even those buildings that have miraculously survived perfectly recreate the picture of the distant past. The Great Silk Road, one of the most significant achievements in the history of world civilization, also ran through these cities. Much effort has been made to ensure a comfortable and safe stay for tourists in these historical cities, which are still filled with the spirit of antiquity to this day. In this regard, a large number of new hotels and guest houses are opening, new restaurants and cafes are reaching international standards, modern vehicles, from cars to comfortable tourist buses, are transporting an increasing number of tourists.

Traveling through Uzbekistan with its historical, archaeological, architectural and natural sites is a real adventure, replete with pleasant discoveries. It is Uzbekistan (among other countries in the region) that is the leader in the market for cultural and educational trips. Guests of our country have the opportunity to trace its history not only in museums, looking at exhibits, but also “live”. One has only to set foot on the land of ancient settlements, visit archaeological sites, and doors will open before you into the distant past of palaces, temples dedicated to various gods, and the lives of people of bygone eras.

You will never forget the tall minarets, grandiose madrassas and mosques, luxurious palaces and austere mausoleums, decorated with incredibly beautiful ceramic ornaments. You will always remember the noisy and colorful oriental bazaars, interesting legends, warm hospitality and ancient traditions of the local residents.

This land full of oriental romance cannot leave anyone indifferent. It is a land of cotton and orchards, never-ending bazaars and skilled artisans who today practice production methods inherited from their ancestors.

Deserts are the center of the ancient formation of species, caravan routes crossing the vast expanses of hot sands and dunes, endless steppes that remain silent and attract with their mystery and immensity have been part of the Great Silk Road since ancient times, connecting ancient China with Europe.

Modern tourist infrastructure also offers travel through the steppes and deserts with unique opportunities to ride camels, live in a yurt (the only human dwelling in the vast expanses of deserts and steppes), equipped with the necessary conditions for tourists to live, and spend an evening by the fire listening to the songs of the local population.

The mountains of Uzbekistan are also the most picturesque landscapes in Central Asia. These amazing places should be seen by anyone who wants to feel the harmony of merging with nature, escape from reality and reflect on life. Forests giving way to mountain meadows turn into mountain peaks and glaciers covered with eternal snow. The inaccessible peaks of the Western Tien Shan, mountain pastures, ridges and fast rivers sparkling under the blue sky have attracted the attention of tourists for many years. In the summer, mountain tourism in Uzbekistan offers a wide range of services on bicycle tracks, hiking, trekking, rafting, mountaineering, horseback riding tours and recreation in fashionable mountain resorts. In winter, snowboarding and paragliding are very popular. Professional instructors provide a high level of service and the implementation of all your most extreme ideas.

And most importantly, the traditions of Uzbek hospitality, deeply rooted in the people, local customs and excellent national cuisine make Uzbekistan an attractive place where guests from all over the world come. You will never forget your trip to Uzbekistan.

But Uzbekistan is not only hoary antiquity, the unique cultural heritage of its people, hospitality and famous national cuisine. Uzbekistan is also modernity, an excellent place for recreation and entertainment, a new, intensively developing tourist destination!

Interesting, cheap, clean, safe - these are the pillars on which what is called an exciting trip to Uzbekistan is based.

Now let's take a closer look at these four trump cards:

Interesting. The rich history of the region, world-famous monuments of architecture and applied art, tours of the ancient cities of Uzbekistan, stories of professional guides that you want to listen to endlessly - this is what awaits you.

Cheap. All tourists coming to Uzbekistan note one indisputable fact: in Uzbekistan, prices for everything are simply "ridiculous," indecently modest. Therefore, spending money here is a pleasure. Shopping in stores of any level and capabilities, entertainment venues, excellent restaurants offering cuisine from around the world, magnificent ski resorts, the capital's special "nightlife" and entertainment - this is what attracts.

Purely. On the streets of Tashkent and other large cities of Uzbekistan, you will not trip over beer bottles, crush empty cigarette packs, or walk around heaps of garbage. Unusually clean, wide, shady streets, green parks, transparent fountains - this is what captivates.

Safely. One can only envy the stability in Uzbekistan. Glory to Allah, the merciful and merciful, there are no wars, no revolutions, no rebellions, no destruction. The population is famous for its peacefulness - this is what makes us remember and dream about Uzbekistan

List of references:

1. Farmanov E. A., Kadyrov D. Kh., Khodzhaeva F. N. The role of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan in the development of tourism // Bulletin of Science and Education. – 2020. – No. 2-3 (80). – pp. 20-23.

2. 4. Ochilova Kh. F. Strategy for demographic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. //Education and problems of social development. – pp. 117-125. 2020 <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=429982593>. Ashurova Sh.A. The wonders of the unexplored cave in Uzbekistan. American Journal of Business Management, Economics and Banking ISSN (E): 2832-8078 Volume 9, | Feb., 2023

4. Ashurova Sh.A. The features of the development of pilgrimage tourism in the world economy TJE - Thematic journal of Education ISSN 2249-9822 Vol-7- Issue Q3- 2022 <http://thematicsjournals.in/index.php/tjed> DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6674372> UIF 2020= 7.528 IFS 2020= 7.433 2022 s

j 5. Ashurova Sh.A. The impact of the digitalization in Uzbekistan's tourism to the economy. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF LIFE SAFETY AND STABILITY (EJLSS) ISSN2660-9630 www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org Volume 28, April-2023.

a 6. <http://mitc.uz/uz/news/view/1186>

c 7. <https://www.technoman.uz/post/raqamli-iqtisodiyot-nima.html>

t 8. <https://www.khabar.uz/uz/tehnologiya/koreya-uzbekistanda-elektron-hukumatni-rovijlandan>

r 9. <https://lex.uz/docs/4143186?ONDATE=15.01.2022>

4

.

5

4

9

p

p

.

-

.